

Application of Strategic Performance Measures in Small and Medium-Sized Manufacturing Enterprises in Kenya: The Use of the Balanced Scorecard Perspectives

¹⁾**Chimwani, Pamela Muhenje**, School of Business, Kabarak University, PO Box Private Bag, 20157, Kabarak, Kenya

²⁾**Onserio Nyamwange**, Department of Management Science, University of Nairobi.

³⁾**Dr. Otuya Robert**, School of Business, Kabarak University, PO Box Private Bag, 20157, Kabarak, Kenya

Abstract:

This study sought to determine the application of Balanced Scorecard in measuring performance in small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises (SMEs) in Kenya. The research design was a survey conducted on a target population of the manufacturing companies in Nairobi from which the stratified sampling technique was used to come up with a sample size of 100 SMEs. The study used questionnaires in data collection. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in analyzing the data. One-way analysis of variance between and within groups was used to develop comparisons to determine the relationship between knowledge of each BSC measurement perspective and its application in manufacturing SMEs. Frequencies, mean and standard deviation were used to draw the descriptive statistics. The study found that there was a gap between the knowledge of customer perspective, internal business perspective and innovation/learning and growth perspective measures and their application in SMEs. Since value is created through internal business processes and innovation and learning /growth, the study recommends that manufacturing SMEs in Nairobi should strive to understand how they view these elements as a major aspect of their performance measurement. Business managers should identify the critical internal business processes which the firm must excel at and should identify the infrastructure that the organization must build to create long- term growth and improvement of its people, systems and organizational structure. For manufacturing SMEs this will eventually translate to the competitiveness hence profitability of the firms.

Key Words: Strategic Performance Measures, Balanced Score Card, Small and Medium Enterprises, Kenya.

1.1 Introduction

It is widely acknowledged among management authorities and practitioners that what you cannot measure, you cannot effectively manage. Performance measurement can be defined as the process of quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of action (Neely et al, 2005). It is “the periodic measurement of progress toward explicit short-run and long run objectives and the reporting of the results to decision makers in an attempt to improve program performance” (Neely et al, 1995). Many authors argue that performance measurement constitutes the most critical activity within the performance management cycle, and that it is necessary for effective deployment of strategy throughout the organization.

Organizations are now adopting business strategies that take into account quality of service, flexibility, customization, innovation, rapid response, customer service, and other such attributes that can broadly be

described as non-financial measures (Atkinson and Brown, 2001). The main function of performance measurement in a strategic context, as suggested by Letza (1996), is to provide the means of control to achieve the objectives required in order to fulfill the company’s mission/strategy statement. This view is supported by Neely et al. (1994) who view performance measurement as a key part of “strategic control”. Fawcett et al (1997) develop this argument by stating the need for performance measurement to exercise this control through: helping managers to identify good performance, setting targets and demonstrating success or failure.

Development of an effective measurement system is a crucial task for any organization exposed to tough competition (Thakkar et al, 2007) and it must be an integral part of the management process. Measurement is difficult in organizations because it is not an exact science with hard rules and predictable interrelationships between variables (Brown, 2000). The balanced

scorecard (BSC) measurement framework view of classifying and relating performance measures is based on four perspectives namely; financial perspectives, customer perspectives, internal process perspectives and innovation and learning/growth perspectives. Introduced by Kaplan and Norton (1992), it is a framework that facilitates the translation of strategy into controllable performance measures. The BSC has a characteristic of comprehensiveness which involves the provision of performance measures in the four perspectives (Decoene and Bruggemen, 2006); the central idea being to complement traditional financial performance measures with non-financial performance measures. It also has the characteristic of linking performance measures with a company's specific strategy and value drivers. Thus, the BSC links performance measures and operational actions to the business strategy to motivate employees to achieve the organizational objectives (Nanni et al, 1992).

Small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) are defined by a number of factors and criteria, such as location, size, age, structure, organization, number of employees, sales volume, worth of assets, ownership through innovation and technology. In this paper the definition according to number of employees was adopted. According to KIRDI (1997) directory, a small and medium-sized firm is one with between five to forty-nine employees.

SMEs are considered the engine of economic growth in most countries. Within the manufacturing industry they have long been recognized as the key drivers of the sector. They contribute in providing job opportunities and act as suppliers of goods and services to large organizations. They act as specialist suppliers of components, parts, and sub-assemblies to larger companies because the items can be produced at a cheaper price than the large companies could achieve in-house. Lack of product quality supplied by them could adversely affect the competitive ability of the larger organizations.

Ghobadian and Gallear (1997) studied the development of TQM in SMEs and found that resource implications particularly that of management time was markedly more taxing for SMEs than larger companies. The resource limitations associated with SMEs indicated that the dimensions of quality and time were critical to ensure that waste levels were kept low, and that a high

level of productivity performance was attained. Similarly, the reliance on a small number of customers suggested that to remain competitive, SMEs have to ensure that customer satisfaction remained high and that they had to be flexible enough to respond rapidly to changes in the market.

Lack of a monetary safety for SMEs to absorb the impact of short term fluctuations resulting from change means that the financial dimension of performance is more critical for them than their larger counterparts. The effective monitoring of the human resource dimension of SMEs is also paramount as the flatter structure of SMEs means that employees often have a greater number of job roles and more responsibility. In these circumstances, a well-trained and motivated workforce is important. Santori and Anderson (1987) stressed the importance of non-financial measures in monitoring and motivating the progress of the human factor of the organization.

Majority of SMEs have simple systems and procedures, which allow flexibility, immediate feedback, short decision-making chain, better understanding and quicker response to customer needs than larger organizations. In spite of these supporting characteristics of SMEs, they are under tremendous pressure to sustain their competitiveness in domestic as well as global markets. Owing to global competition, technological advances and changing needs of consumers, competitive paradigms are continuously changing. These changes are driving firms to compete, simultaneously along different dimensions such as design and development of product, manufacturing, distribution, communication and marketing.

With globalization of markets, SMEs have many opportunities to work in integration with large-scale organizations. Although the SMEs exhibit distinct characteristics that differentiate them from the majority of their larger counterparts, there is a need to establish the relevance of existing performance measurement approaches for SMEs and to identify an appropriate process for the design and implementation of strategic performance measurement systems in their context (Storey, 1994). If they focus on strategic performance measurement SMEs can exploit the opportunities presented to them and sustain their competitiveness in the current business environment, which is increasingly being driven more by value than by cost. In summary,

there are compelling reasons why performance measurement especially in SMEs must become more strategic in outlook. Models and mechanisms must be developed to address the need for appropriate supporting performance measures for manufacturing strategy for SMEs in the rapidly changing business environment.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The role of SMEs in a national economy has been emphasized all over the world, considering their contribution to the total manufacturing output and employment opportunities. SMEs in Kenya employed some 3.2 million people in 2003 and accounted for 18 per cent of national GDP (African Development Bank and OECD Development Centre, African Economic Outlook, 2004-2005). Hence, there is potential to improve the overall performance of SMEs and their competitiveness, through strategic performance measurement. Large-scale manufacturing enterprises are effectively using strategic performance measurement to improve productivity and quality and hence the competitiveness of manufacturing (Nyamwange, 2001). However, strategic performance measurement has received little attention from SMEs although it has an important role to play in improving the competitiveness of SMEs in a global market (Dwyer, 2007). Furthermore, Inadequate or inappropriate measures are what make firms fail (McAdam & Bailie 2002). Indeed as Hudson et al. (2001) found that 'current literature is inadequate in respect of the specific SME context, Mintzberg et al (1998) also observed that there is a distinct scarcity of strategic planning in the majority of SMEs. The significant differences in the structure and philosophy of SMEs indicate a need to assess the relevance of the strategic performance measurement development process, and this includes performance measures applied and how these are aligned to organizational strategy. This study therefore assessed the performance measures applied by SMEs and how these are aligned to organizational strategy.

1.3 Research Objectives

Two objectives were identified as follows:

1. To determine the performance measures used in SMEs within the manufacturing sector in Nairobi
2. To determine the relationship between knowledge of each of BSC measurement

perspective and its application in SMEs within the manufacturing sector in Nairobi.

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

There has been a change of focus about what drives performance in today's business environment. Atkinson et al (2005) identify some of the elements that have caused this change as: the changing nature of work, increased competition, specific improvement initiatives, national and international quality awards, changing internal and external demands (stakeholders), accelerated technological advancement, changing organizational roles and the acceleration of globalization. All these phenomena pose challenges to SMEs in the current complex and competitive business environment. Therefore, SMEs must develop themselves strategically so as to remain competitive, grow and prosper. As they may have to be faced with global competition, many manufacturing SMES are feeling the pressure from their major customers and prime contractors to implement new types of manufacturing practices such as just-in-time production in order to become world-class enterprises (Hendry, 1998).

SMEs usually behave in a reactive manner, therefore the level of strategic planning is poor and there are no formalized decision-making processes. This lack of explicit strategies and methodologies to support the control process leads to both a short-term vision and orientation (Garengo and Bititci, 2007). In the majority of SMEs, strategy is often implicit and is the result of the goals and preference of the entrepreneur alone.

2.2 Performance Measures and Strategy

The definition of performance measures and the setting of targets for these measures are concrete formulations of a firm's strategic choices (Wouters and Sportel, 2006). Competing on the basis of non-financial factors means that organizations need information on how well they are performing across a broad spectrum of dimensions. Performance information about markets and customers, competitive position, financial performance, customer service performance, operational performance, suppliers' performance, and so on needs to be integrated, dynamic,

accurate, accessible and visible to aid fast decision-making and to promote a proactive management style leading to agility and responsiveness. The link to strategy is subtle, but powerful: measures that are aligned with strategy not only provide information on whether the strategy is being implemented, but also encourage behaviors consistent with the strategy (Kaplan and Norton, 1992).

Accepting Mintzberg's (1998) thesis that when an organization realizes that the strategy is a function of the "pattern of decisions and actions" it takes, it then becomes clear that appropriately designed performance measures can encourage the implementation of strategy. Business performance measures are one way of providing information about where the organization is heading. Leading organizations are using their measurement systems as a means of communicating to their employees what is important. Therefore, there is need for appropriate performance measures so that performance gaps, performance shortfalls, even performance advantages are identified.

Organizations are being forced to consider quality, customer service, response and other such attributes, given that today's markets are driven more by value than cost. This has generated the need for performance measures that facilitate the control of these attributes (Bourne et al, 2000). As the pace of change continues to accelerate in the global economy it is important for firms to move beyond financial performance measures and to consider non-financial performance variables that contribute to long-term value creation (Barksy and Bremser, 1999).

Medori and Steeple (2000) outline some of the advantages and disadvantages of using non-financial measures. These measures are timelier than the traditional financial ones; the measures are very measurable and precise; they are meaningful to the workforce thus facilitating continuous improvement; they are consistent with company goals and strategies; and they are flexible and dynamic, and therefore are able to change, as market needs change. One of the main disadvantages is that there is an abundance of non-financial measures and one of the major problems is knowing which measure to use effectively (Stiver et al, 1998).

2.4 Strategic Performance Measurement Systems

Neely (1999) states that there has been an increased interest in more strategic performance measurement systems since the late 1980s. According to Ittner et al (2003) a strategic performance measurement system is a system that provides information that allows the firm to identify the strategies offering the highest potential for achieving the firm's objectives and aligns management processes, such as target setting, decision-making and performance evaluation, with the achievement of the chosen strategic objectives.

Gates (1999) defines strategic performance measurement as a system that "translates business strategies into deliverable results. It combines financial, strategic, and operating business measures to gauge how well a company meets its targets. Strategic performance measurement systems are based on the strategic options adopted by organizations and help them to build organizational capabilities to sustain their competitiveness (Mohamed et al, 2008). They are based on organizational objectives, critical success factors, and customer needs and monitor both the financial and non-financial aspects (Manoochehri, 1999). They change dynamically with the strategy and they meet the need of specific situations in manufacturing operations and are long-term oriented as well as simple to understand and implement (Santori and Anderson, 1987).

With the business environment having evolved dramatically over the last four decades, performance management and evaluation has become the focus in recent years. Almost every aspect of organizations and management has had to change accordingly and more appropriate measurement tools developed to enhance business competitiveness. Recent years have seen the development of a number of frameworks and models for performance measurement. Performance measurement models or approaches that have evolved since the 1980s are: the Strategic Measurement And Reporting Technique (SMART), the Performance Matrix, the Performance Pyramid, the Business Excellence Model, the Performance Pyramid System, the Balanced Scorecard, the Results and Determinants Framework, the Cambridge Performance Measurement Systems Design Process, the Macro Process Model, the Integrated Performance Measurement Systems (IPMS), the Performance Prism and the Six Sigma. Their main

purpose being to help organizations build organizational capabilities to sustain continuous improvement and hence competitiveness by incorporating a very wide range non-financial measures which include among others: customer satisfaction, quality and delivery, the business's products processes (cycle time and waste), direct personnel measures (Hudson et al, 2001), and measures of intellectual capital and measures that reflect intangible assets.

The research findings of Hudson et al (2000) undertaken to evaluate the appropriateness of strategic performance measurement system development processes for SMEs indicate a discontinuity between current theory and the requirements of practitioners in small companies. One of the recommendations they make is that the relevance of existing approaches needs to be established and appropriate processes for the design and implementation of strategic performance measurement for SMEs identified. A set of requirements for a SME focused strategic performance measurement development process is then specified.

2.3 Traditional Performance Measures

Performance measurement using traditional financial performance measures is characterized by a cost accounting orientation which emphasizes selective financial indicators such as profit and return on investment (Gomes et al, 2006). Managers strive to minimize the variances from standard rather than seek to improve continually and this may lead to local optimization. The measurement provides inadequate information for productivity measurement and improvement programs (Banker et al, 1989). Furthermore they also give misleading signals for continuous improvement and innovation (Kaplan and Norton, 1992).

Fawcett et al (1997), state that traditional financial measures have a narrow scope and do not provide understanding and integration of the critical factors (quality, responsiveness and flexibility, what customers want, the competition) that create the foundation of future business success. They are therefore are not adequate for business evaluation (Drucker, 1993).

Various authorities have put forward different classifications to appropriately describe traditional

accounting performance measures such as being "Lag indicators" and "Backward looking measures"(Bourne et al., 2000) ; Cumby and Conrod, 2001). "Lag ex-post indicators" (Nixon, 1998). This implies that they have a historical focus, reporting on outcomes, which are consequences of past actions. Baully (1994) described them as "Static metrics". As a result they fail to facilitate responsiveness and agility (Bititci et al, 1998) because they are insensitive to changes in the internal and external environment of the firm.

Drucker (1990) asserted that they are inappropriate in modern manufacturing settings, as they said nothing about the factors, such as customer service innovation, the percent of first-time quality, and employee development that actually help grow market share and profits. They also lack the ability to guide the firm in its efforts to achieve manufacturing excellence. In summary, these views suggest that traditional financial accounting paradigms do not reflect performance in the new economy and are, therefore, inadequate for evaluating an organization's strategic performance. According to Garengo and Bititci (2007) the majority of SMEs focus on accounting aspects, as their approach to performance measurement is traditional as it is based on financial measures.

2.6 The Balanced Score Card and Strategic Performance Measurement

An important issue in regard to strategic performance measurement and SMEs is the enabling role that can be played by the balance scorecard (BSC) to align performance measures and strategy based on the four perspectives of the BSC namely; financial perspectives, customer perspectives, internal process perspectives and innovation and learning/growth perspectives.

The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) is a strategic performance management tool for measuring whether the smaller-scale operational activities of a company are aligned with its larger-scale objectives in terms of vision and strategy. It focuses not only on financial outcomes but also on non-financial inputs of these. The BSC helps provide a more comprehensive view of a business, which in turn helps organizations act in their best long-term interests. The underlying rationale is that organizations cannot directly influence financial outcomes, as these are "lag" measures, and that the use

of financial measures alone to inform the strategic control of the firm is unwise.

Organizations should instead also measure those areas where direct management intervention is possible. Clear definitions of each perspective, which constitute the main characteristics of key performance indicators in manufacturing, are given by various authorities as financial, customer, internal business process and innovation and learning/growth.

2.6.1 Financial Perspective

Financial measures remain an important dimension within the BSC. Financial performance measures indicate whether a company's strategy, implementation, and execution are contributing to bottom-line improvement. They indicate how well a company is performing with respect to its profitability targets (Decoene and Bruggeman, 2006). They have to do with a firm's performance and resource management. Financial performance measures are retrospective performance measures that reflect the results of past managerial actions and an exclusive reliance on them causes organizations to sub-optimize (Kaplan and Norton, 1996).

From a financial perspective, return on equity, return on assets, cash flow, earnings per share, sales, earnings before income tax (EBIT), sales/ total assets, return on capital employed, fixed costs, labour costs, scrap, rework, revenue growth, profit margins, cash flow and net operating income are performance measures generally agreed on.

2.6.2 Customer Perspective

“The Customer is King” is a common adage in business circles. Customer-related measures indicate a company's success in attracting and retaining its targeted customers (Decoene and Bruggeman, 2006). The importance of the customer cannot be overemphasized. According to the findings of a study by Appia-Adu and Singh (1998) of UK SMEs, there is a positive effect of customer orientation on SME performance.

Various authorities have expounded on what it means to be a customer-oriented firm as one, which emphasizes on evaluating and addressing customer needs and which

disseminates information about the customer throughout the organization. This implies that customer information is collected and used by the business to develop strategies to meet customer needs. It implies a culture of being responsive to the customer and putting the customer's interests first, while not excluding those of all other stakeholders such as owners, managers, employees, in order to develop a long-term profitable enterprise.

In their study Appia-Adu and Singh (1998) concluded that SME practitioners that were able to inject customer-oriented measures into their business had a distinct possibility of achieving a competitive edge. They were more likely to be more profitable as they are not only driven to develop new products but develop better value and quality products to relative to their competitors, which is vital for achieving and maintaining superior performance. This would further lead to retention/sales growth and repeat purchases resulting in lower customer acquisition costs, the outcome being improved profitability.

Some of the most common customer measures incorporated are: customer retention, customer acquisition, customer satisfaction, number of new customers referred by existing customers, sales to new customers, number of complaints from customers, identify emerging needs of existing customers, price sensitivity surveys, % sales from new products, returns by customers and break even time for new products, customization of products according to customer needs and response time for ‘specials’.

2.6.3 Internal Business Process Perspective

Internal business process measures indicate the level of a company's performance with respect to activities that are critical to meet customer and financial objectives (Decoene and Bruggeman, 2006). They also indicate what the firm must do internally to meet its customers' expectations. The core competencies and the critical technologies are identified and measured to ensure market leadership (Thakkar et al, 2007).

They have to be carefully designed by those who know the internal processes of the firm most intimately, as they should be derived from the firm's unique vision and mission statement/strategy. A decision is then made

about what processes and competencies the firm must excel at and measures specified for each. The measures address the issues of cost, quality, efficiency, productivity, employee skills and other characteristics of goods and services.

General internal business process perspective measures specific to manufacturing are: output per employee or per labour-hour, time spent on each stage of product development, time to process an operation, number of errors per unit, production volume, number of incidents/accidents/ and illness rate, measures of rework, downtime, idle time and scrap.

2.6.4 Innovation/ Learning and Growth Perspective

Innovation and learning/ growth measures indicate a company's success in developing the personnel and systems necessary for growth and product improvement in the long run. It is the foundation perspective upon which all the other three perspectives lie (Kaplan and Norton, 2000). They indicate a firm's ability to respond to changes in technology, customer attitudes and the economic environment.

Many managers concede that this perspective is their weakest link in the application of performance measurement based on the BSC and simply label it employee or people perspective (Marr and Adam, 2004). Kaplan and Norton (2004) have recently articulated the principal components of the innovation and learning/growth perspective as consisting of the intangible assets of the organization namely: human capital (employees' skills, talent, and knowledge); information capital (databases, information systems, networks, and technology infrastructure); organization capital (culture, leadership, employee alignment, teamwork, and knowledge management). The most common measures incorporated are: employee capabilities, motivation, and empowerment, employee satisfaction and employee turnover rate, employee skill level assessments, employee productivity statistics and performance appraisal reports, gender ratios, percentage internal promotions, technology growth, computer systems, and organizational culture.

2.6.5 Strategy Mapping with the BSC

A strategy map is the best tool to operate a BSC (Kaplan and Norton, 2004). A strategy map is a communication tool used to tell a story of how value is created for the organization. It shows a logical, step-by-step connection between strategic objectives in the form of a cause-and-effect chain. Improving performance in the objectives found in the innovation and learning/growth perspective enables the organization to improve its internal process perspective objectives, which in turn enables the organization to create desirable results in the customer and financial perspectives.

Based on the literature review, the following hypotheses were tested.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between knowledge and application of the financial measurement perspective in the BSC

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between knowledge and application of the customer measurement perspective in the BSC

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between knowledge and application of the internal business process measurement perspective in the BSC

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in means between knowledge and application of the innovation/learning and growth measurement perspective in the BSC

3.0 Research Methodology

The research design was a survey conducted on a sample of 100 out of 740 manufacturing firms in five large sub-sectors namely: Food, beverage, tobacco, textile and apparel and leather products; Wood and wood products, paper production, printing and publishing; Chemicals, petroleum, rubber and plastics; Non-metallic mineral products except petroleum products; Metal industries, fabrication of metal products, machinery and equipment. This design borrowed from the Balanced Scorecard perspectives whereby the four perspectives of measurement were explored. Like in Sousa et al (2006), the balanced scorecard (Kaplan and Norton, 1993) perspective was adopted because of its simplicity, general acceptance among practitioners and researchers, and its close association with strategy (Kaplan and Norton, 1996). Thus the research instrument and variables have been structured around the four

perspectives of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC): financial perspective, customer perspective, internal process perspective and innovation and learning/growth perspective. The study relied on primary data collected using a structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions.

The instrument addressed the two research objectives. The first section of the questionnaire sought general information about the particular enterprise such as the name of the business, which manufacturing sub-sector the business belonged to, the number of employees in the firm and the range of the previous year's profit. The second section had close-ended questions based on a six point Likert scale from 0 to 5 (whereby 0= not sure, 1= strongly disagree, 2= agree, 3= neutral, 4= agree and 5= strongly agree) to indicate the level of agreement to statements about performance measures. The third section also had close-ended questions based on a scale of 0 to 5 (whereby 0 = not at all, 1= to a very low extent, 2 = to a low extent 3 = moderately 4 = to a high extent and 5= to a very high extent) to indicate level of application of BSC measurement perspectives.

4.0 Results and Discussions

The study adopted the use of descriptive and inferential statistics in the analysis of the data. Descriptive statistics was employed in the first and second sections of the questionnaire. According to Cooper and Schindler

(1999), descriptive statistics have often been used in exploratory studies.

The third section of the study was analyzed using inferential statistics whereby comparisons were developed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) between and within groups to determine the relationship between knowledge of each BSC measurement perspective and its application in the SMEs.

Majority of SMEs used in the study were from the Metal, Fabrication of metal products, Machinery & Equipment sector as represented by 31.3 percent of the total 96 firms. The next major categories were in Chemicals, Petroleum, Rubber and Plastics Food, Beverage, Tobacco, Textile, Apparel and Leather products in that order. The 17.7 percent of the SMEs that were from other industries not specified in the questionnaire were in moulding, drugs and medicine, detergents, antiseptics, water industry, PVC coated products, automotive spare parts and services, power generation and petrol engine products, transport, electrical appliances, fibre glass fabrication, solar products, plumbing and hardware export. On the number of employees in each business, 32.3 percent of the SMEs had employed more than 40 people, 25 percent had between 11 to 20 employees, and 19.8 percent had below 10 employees while 11.5 percent had between 21 to 30 employees.

4.2. Performance Measures used in Manufacturing SMEs

The study sought to establish the performance measures used and the extent of their application in manufacturing SMEs in Nairobi. The majority of the firms as shown in Table 4.1 had a large percentage of their performance measures in the financial perspectives category.

Table 4.1 Ten most common performance measures

Performance Measures	Percentage of firms with performance measures	Performance measure from BSC Perspective
1. Measures of changes in sales	93%	Financial perspective
2. Measures of relevant product attributes	92%	Internal business process perspective
3. Measures of cash flow	90%	Financial perspective
4. Measures of sales	88%	Financial perspective
5. Measures of incoming materials quality	88%	Internal business process perspective
6. Measures of unit production	88%	Financial perspective

costs		
7. Measures of cost of production	88%	Financial perspective
8. Measures of continuous improvement in processes	88%	Internal business process perspective
9. Measures of cost Vs budget	85%	Financial perspective
10. Measures of a business with a clear business strategy	84%	Internal business process perspective

4.2.1 Financial Perspective Measures

Observations showed that majority of the top most common measures are financial in nature, with measures of changes in sales and cash flow in 93 percent and 90 percent of the firms respectively. Of the SMEs surveyed, on average 88 percent of them had measures for unit production costs, cost of production and cost vs. budget. It is evident that the method of measuring performance in SMEs is focused on financial metrics, which according to Bourne et al., 2000, are lag indicators as they report on outcomes, the consequences of past actions. This heavy reliance on financial indicators promotes short-term behaviour that sacrifices long-term value creation for short term performance (Barksy and Bremser, 1999).

4.2.2 Customer Perspective Measures

In 67 percent of the firms, performance measures were developed by managers and only 45 percent of the firms agreed that customers had an input in developing performance measures. Although 84 percent of the firms had measures for existing customers and 75 percent had measures for new customers. 68 per cent had measures for lost sales and customers. 71 percent agreed that customer needs were placed ahead of the owners and 77 percent customized products according to customer requirements. Nevertheless only 67 percent carried out customer surveys regularly and 59 percent routinely or regularly measured customer service. Firms should strive to be more attentive to customers' needs by letting them have an input in developing measures, and customer satisfaction surveys should be carried as a matter of routine. An improvement in customer satisfaction will not only increase business profits, but also facilitate business development.

4.2.3 Internal Business Process Perspective Measures

Majority of the firms had measures of continuous improvement in processes and measures to do with in-process quality were also agreed upon as being very important for the success of the firm. Most have a clear business strategy and agree that their performance measures were derived from strategy. This agrees with McAdam and Bailey, 2002, that performance measures should be derived from strategy. Nevertheless, 40 percent of the firms did not agree that the firm should have performance measures for management performance. An identical percentage did not have a developed strategy map which is ideally a management function. Firms should ensure that their operational processes can meet customer demands both the current and in the future. Within the manufacturing sphere, this implies an emphasis on reduction in time delays, incomplete work orders and reductions in service time to increase efficiency and achieve customer satisfaction.

4.2.4 Innovation and Learning/Growth Perspective Measures

73 percent of the firms surveyed agreed that they had data on employees' competencies, capabilities and skills. From observations it emerged that 67 percent of them regularly carried out employee satisfaction surveys and 75 percent of the firms surveyed agreed that performance measures provided adequate information for improvement in programmes. However, a paltry 48 percent provided training to employees measures on product quality. The innovation and

learning/growth perspective is the basis of BSC (Kaplan and Norton, 1996). Accordingly, it can become the motivating force for the previous three perspectives achieving excellent performance for the firm. SMEs in the manufacturing sector should provide opportunities for their employees to learn and grow, to focus on their occupation skills, and to acquire secondary skills, which would translate into a more competitive firm. Resources should also be set aside for technological advancement and general improvement of the firms systems and procedures.

4.3 Knowledge and Application of BSC Measurement Perspectives

Questions were asked to find out how the businesses rated their application of performance measures in the groups of BSC measurement perspectives in order to determine the extent of application. The study then sought to establish association between the knowledge and application of various BSC measurement perspectives. The study conducted a one-way analysis for each individual BSC measurement perspective at 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$).

4.3.1. Application of Financial Perspective Measures

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to determine the relationship between knowledge about financial perspective measures and its application in SMEs. Table 4.2 indicates that there was a statistically insignificant difference in the category of regular measurement of operational cost within $p = 0.362$, $p = 0.360$ in the regular measurement of revenue growth category, and also in the category of regular measurement of return on investment within $p = 0.161$. The categories regular measurement of labor cost and regular measurement of earning before tax also registered statistically insignificant differences within $p = 0.435$ and $p = 0.063$ respectively. The category of regular measurement of scrap and re-work and scrap was statistically insignificant within $p = 0.816$. It therefore implies that SMEs in spite of their knowledge of BSC financial perspective there is a gap between knowledge and application of the same.

Table 4.2: ANOVA – Knowledge and Application of Financial Perspective Measures

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Return on Investment	Between Groups	42.408	23	1.844	1.424	.131
	Within Groups	91.950	71	1.295		
	Total	134.358	94			
Earnings before tax	Between Groups	39.776	23	1.729	1.623	.063
	Within Groups	75.656	71	1.066		
	Total	115.432	94			
Labour cost	Between Groups	27.074	23	1.177	1.036	.435
	Within Groups	80.652	71	1.136		
	Total	107.726	94			
Scrap and re-work	Between Groups	35.958	23	1.563	.713	.816
	Within Groups	155.578	71	2.191		
	Total	191.537	94			
Revenue growth	Between Groups	27.972	23	1.216	1.107	.360
	Within Groups	78.028	71	1.099		
	Total	106.000	94			
Operational cost	Between Groups	21.436	23	.932	1.105	.362
	Within Groups	59.869	71	.843		
	Total	81.305	94			

4.3.2 Application of Customer Perspective Measures

The one-way ANOVA was conducted to explore the relationship between knowledge about BSC customer perspective measures and its application in the SMEs (Table 4.3). It was found that there was a statistically insignificant difference in the speed of response to customers category within $p= 0.07$, inclusion of new customer requirements in product design within $p= 0.056$ and goods returned to customers category within $p= 0.230$. The categories of number of new customers $p=0.428$ and customer retention/Repeat sales showed that there was statistically insignificant difference within $p= 0.428$ and $p=0.508$ respectively. It, therefore, follows that the SMEs do not apply the knowledge they have on BSC customer perspective measures.

Table 1.3: ANOVA – Knowledge and Application of Customer Perspective Measures

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Goods returned by customers	Between Groups	65.419	20	3.271	1.265	.230
	Within Groups	191.381	74	2.586		
	Total	256.800	94			
Number of new customers	Between Groups	32.580	20	1.629	1.041	.428
	Within Groups	115.778	74	1.565		
	Total	148.358	94			
Customer retention/Repeat sales	Between Groups	33.457	20	1.673	.969	.508
	Within Groups	127.764	74	1.727		
	Total	161.221	94			
Inclusion of new customer requirement in Product design	Between Groups	43.127	20	2.156	1.683	.056
	Within Groups	94.831	74	1.281		
	Total	137.958	94			
Response to customers	Between Groups	31.499	20	1.575	1.623	.070
	Within Groups	71.828	74	.971		
	Total	103.326	94			

4.3.3 Application of Internal Business Process Perspective Measures

A one-way ANOVA was carried out as shown Table 4.4 It found that there was a statistical significant difference within the time spent on each stage of product development category where $p= 0.013$. However, there was a statistical insignificant difference in the determination of number of errors category within $p= 0.360$, the dependent variable of output per employee or per labour hour within $p= 0.227$ and category of measures of rework within $p= 0.118$. Also in the categories of occurrence of injuries/accidents and measures of downtime or idle time within $p= 0.617$ and $p=0.503$ respectively. From the observations above, it can be implied that the SMEs do apply their knowledge on internal business process perspective measure with regard to time spent on each stage of product development category. However, other measures such as output per employee or per labour, measures of rework, occurrence of injuries/accidents and measures of downtime or idle time were applied to a less extent.

Table 4.4: ANOVA – Knowledge and Application of Internal Business Process Perspective Measures

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Output per employee or per labor hour	Between Groups	105.481	40	2.637	1.242	.227
	Within Groups	114.667	54	2.123		
	Total	220.147	94			
Time spent on each stage of product development	Between Groups	125.605	40	3.140	1.916	.013
	Within Groups	88.500	54	1.639		
	Total	214.105	94			
Number of errors	Between Groups	92.897	40	2.322	1.107	.360
	Within Groups	113.250	54	2.097		
	Total	206.147	94			
Number of injuries/accidents	Between Groups	96.708	40	2.418	.911	.617
	Within Groups	143.250	54	2.653		
	Total	239.958	94			
Measures of downtime and idle time	Between Groups	113.155	40	2.829	.994	.503
	Within Groups	153.750	54	2.847		
	Total	266.905	94			
Measures of rework	Between Groups	122.304	40	3.058	1.412	.118
	Within Groups	116.917	54	2.165		
	Total	239.221	94			

4.3.4 Application of Innovation/Learning and Growth Perspective Measures

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to investigate the relationship between knowledge about BSC innovation/learning perspective and its application in the SMEs Table 4.5. It was found that there was a statistically insignificant difference within the employee performance category within $p = 0.054$, training provided to employees on product quality within $p = 0.161$, the measures of skill level category within $p = 0.483$ and also the measures of technological improvement category whereby $p = 0.316$. However, the categories of skills improvement activities and training and also employee satisfaction surveys showed statistically significant differences within $p = 0.044$ and within $p = 0.001$ respectively. It, therefore, follows that the SMEs do not apply the knowledge they have on innovation/learning and growth perspective measures with regard to employee performance, their skill/ training level and technological improvement. But they do apply measures of skills improvement activities and training and employee satisfaction surveys.

Table 4.5: ANOVA – Knowledge and Application of Innovation/Learning and Growth Perspective Measures

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Training provided to employees on product quality	Between Groups	64.808	20	3.240	1.377	.161
	Within Groups	176.525	75	2.354		
	Total	241.333	95			
Measures of skill level	Between Groups	27.406	20	1.370	.991	.483
	Within Groups	103.750	75	1.383		
	Total	131.156	95			
Surveys of employees satisfaction/attitudes	Between Groups	67.700	20	3.385	2.855	.001
	Within Groups	88.925	75	1.186		
	Total	156.625	95			
Employee Performance	Between Groups	50.300	20	2.515	1.689	.054
	Within Groups	111.658	75	1.489		
	Total	161.958	95			
Measures of Technological employment	Between Groups	40.040	20	2.002	1.156	.316
	Within Groups	129.867	75	1.732		
	Total	169.906	95			
Skills of improvement activities and training	Between Groups	61.940	20	3.097	1.744	.044
	Within Groups	133.217	75	1.776		
	Total	195.156	95			

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The aim of the study was to establish the performance measures used in the small and medium-sized manufacturing firms in Nairobi and to determine the extent of application of performance measures using the balance scorecard measurement perspectives. The study targeted 100 manufacturing SMEs listed in the KIRDI (1997) directory. Responses were received from 96 firms representing a response rate of 96 percent. Primary data was collected through a questionnaire with close-ended questions that enabled the collection of quantitative data.

The study found that the most common performance measures in manufacturing SMEs in Nairobi were financial in nature. However, the existence of measures from the internal business process and the innovation and learning/growth perspectives and their application was not very obvious. The findings indicated overall, that there was a gap between the knowledge of customer perspective measures, internal business perspective measures and innovation/learning and growth

perspective measures and their application in SMEs in Nairobi. These generally concur with Sousa et al (2006) findings, on performance measures adopted by English SMEs, that there was a gap between the theory/knowledge of performance measures and the practice.

The study recommends that manufacturing SMEs in Nairobi should supplement the traditional financial measures with non-financial measures: customer perspective measures, internal business perspectives measures and innovation and learning/growth measures. Since value is created through customers, manufacturing SMEs may need to interrogate how they view these elements as a major aspect of their performance measurement. Business managers may also need to identify the critical internal business processes which the firm must excel at and hence identify the infrastructure that the organization must build to create long- term growth and improvement (Kaplan and Norton, 2000) of its people, systems and organizational structure.

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